

Triphenylsiloxy and Diphenylsilyloxy Derivatives of Boron[†]

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Tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane, phenyl *bis*(triphenylsiloxy)borane, 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxa-borolanes, -borinanes, -borole and -borin and diphenyl *bis*(1,3,2-dioxa-borolane-2-oxy)silanes have been synthesized by various routes and the reactivity of Si-O-B linkage has been compared with that of Ge-O-B and Sn-O-B linkages. *Tris*(triphenylsiloxy)-borane reacts with acetic acid by cleavage of Si-O bond to give triphenylsilyl acetate and boric acid. 2-Triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole forms 1:1 addition complexes with pyridine, triethylamine and aniline. Condensation of diphenylsilane diol with boric acid, *tri*(isopropoxy)borane or phenyldihydroxyborane yields cyclic derivatives.

METALLOSILOXANES, containing a metal-oxygen-silicon linkage, have been explored^{1,2} mainly due to two reasons: (a) to attempt the synthesis of siloxane polymers with special properties by incorporating different metal atoms in the siloxane chain and (b) to compare the properties of metal siloxides with metal alkoxides. Trimethylsiloxides of a large number of main group³ as well as transition metals⁴ have been studied. The corresponding triphenylsiloxy derivatives of only a few elements have been described so far and these show considerable thermal and hydrolytic stability in comparison to trimethylsiloxy derivatives^{1,2}. The present paper deals with the synthesis and reactions of triphenylsiloxy and diphenylsilyloxy derivatives of boron.

Although there is considerable literature on siloxyboranes⁵, the only triphenylsiloxy derivative described so far is B(OSiPh₃)₃, obtained by esterification of boric acid with triphenylsilanol⁶. Other monomeric siloxyboranes have been synthesized by various routes which are, in general, extensions of those used for the synthesis of alkoxyboranes. One of us has recently reported the synthesis of various trimethylsiloxyboranes by cleavage reactions of stannoxyboranes with trimethylchlorosilane⁷.

Experimental

Triphenylsilanol (B.D.H.) and diphenylsilane diol (Alfa Inorganics) were used as supplied. *Tri*(isopropoxy)borane and 2-isopropoxy-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane were prepared by published procedures.

Boron was estimated by Thomas's method. Silicon was estimated as silica. Isopropanol was estimated by oxidation with chromic acid. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene. IR and pmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-337 and Perkin-Elmer R12B spectrometers respectively.

Tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane: A mixture of *tri*(isopropoxy)borane (0.54 g; 2.9 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.30 g; 8.3 mmol) in benzene (60 ml) was refluxed for about 3 hr and the azeotrope was fractionated (amount of isopropanol in azeotrope: Found, 0.45 g. Calcd. 0.52 g). Excess of solvent was distilled out and the white solid product (2.32 g, m.p. 148°) was finally dried under reduced pressure (Found: B, 1.23; Si, 10.02%; M, 815. Calcd. for C₂₄H₄₈BO₃Si₃; B, 1.29; Si, 10.08%; M, 836).

Attempted synthesis of (isopropoxy) (triphenylsiloxy)boranes: (a) A mixture of *tri*(isopropoxy)borane (1.74 g; 9.3 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.56 g; 9.3 mmol) was refluxed in benzene (40 ml) for about one hour and fractionated (Found: isopropanol 0.53 g. Calcd. 0.56 g). Removal of solvent at 30°/0.01 mm yielded *tris*(triphenylsiloxy)borane (2.55 g, m.p. 148°) (Found: B, 1.20; Si, 9.92%).

(b) Reaction between *tri*(isopropoxy)borane (0.77 g; 4.1 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.26 g; 8.2 mmol) in benzene (60 ml) was carried out as in previous experiment yielding isopropanol (Found: 0.42 g. Calcd. 0.49 g) and *tris*(triphenylsiloxy)borane (2.28 g, m.p. 148°) (Found: B, 1.14; Si, 10.05%).

Phenyl bis(triphenylsiloxy)borane: Azeotropic removal of water from a mixture of phenyldihydroxyborane (0.56 g; 4.6 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.51 g; 9.1 mmol) in benzene (40 ml) followed by drying the product under reduced pressure yielded a white solid (2.92 g, m.p. 134°) (Found: B, 1.55; Si, 8.60%; M, 664. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₈BO₂Si₂; B, 1.70; Si, 8.80%; M, 638).

2-Triphenylsiloxy-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane: (a) Refluxing a mixture of 2-isopropoxy-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane (1.86 g; 10.0 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.76 g; 10.0 mmol) in benzene (60 ml) for one hour, followed by fractionation yielded isopropanol (Found: 0.52 g. Calcd.

[†] Dedicated to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, our teacher and guide, on the occasion of his sixtieth birthday.

TABLE 1--SYNTHESIS OF SOME NEW 2-TRIPHENYLSILOXY-1,3,2-DIOXABOROLANES, -BOROLE, -BORIN AND -BORINANES

Sl. No.	Triphenyl silanol (g) (mmol)	G in G(OH) ₂ (g) (mmol)	Boric acid (g) (mmol)	Product; Molecular formula, Nature	Yield (g) (%)	b.p. (°C/mm) m.p. (°C)	Analysis (%)		Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)
							Boron Found (Calcd.)	Silicon Found (Calcd.)	
1.	2.5 (10.0)	-CHMeCH ₂ - 0.76 (10.0)	0.61 (9.8)	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ BO ₂ Si Viscous liquid	2.62 (74)	215/1.5	3.18 (3.01)	7.14 (7.80)	385 (360)
2.	1.45 (8.9)	-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ - 0.68 (8.9)	0.55 (8.9)	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ BO ₂ Si White solid	2.62 (82)	215/1.0 (70)	3.00 (3.01)	7.71 (7.80)	352 (360)
3.	2.23 (8.1)	-CHMeCH ₂ CH ₂ - 0.74 (8.3)	0.51 (8.2)	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ BO ₂ Si White solid	2.62 (84)	224/0.5 (60)	2.79 (2.92)	7.37 (7.51)	370 (374)
4.	2.44 (8.8)	-CMe ₂ CMe ₂ - 1.07 (9.1)	0.55 (8.9)	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ BO ₂ Si White solid	3.27 (92)	192/0.3 (146)	2.60 (2.69)	6.94 (6.99)	396 (402)
5.	2.46 (8.9)	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ - 0.98 (8.9)	0.55 (8.9)	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ BO ₂ Si Viscous liquid	3.51 (100)	—	2.71 (2.75)	7.08 (7.13)	383 (394)
6.	2.57 (9.3)	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ - 1.16 (9.4)	0.58 (9.4)	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ BO ₂ Si Light yellow solid	3.80 (100)	(101)	2.49 (2.65)	6.37 (6.88)	401 (408)

0.60 g) in the azeotrope. On removing excess of solvent *in vacuo*, the desired product (3.66 g, m.p. 82°; b.p. 217°/0.05 mm) was obtained as a light yellow solid (Found: B, 2.51; Si, 6.52%; M, 368. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₇BO₂Si; B, 2.69; Si, 6.99%; M, 402).

(b) 2,2'-(1,1,3-Trimethyltrimethylenedioxy)bis-(4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane (1.23 g; 3.3 mmol) was added to *tris*(triphenylsiloxy)borane (2.79 g; 3.3 mmol) in benzene (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. Removing the solvent under reduced pressure and subsequent distillation at 217°/0.05 mm yielded 2-triphenylsiloxy-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane as a light yellow solid, (3.54 g, m.p. 82°) (Found: B, 2.46; Si, 6.31%).

(c) Azeotropic removal of water from a mixture of triphenylsilanol (4.51 g; 16.3 mmol) and 2,2'-oxybis(4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane) (2.20 g; 8.1 mmol) in benzene (60 ml) gave a light yellowish solid (6.13 g, m.p. 82°; b.p. 217°/0.05 mm) (Found: B, 2.40; Si, 6.80%).

2-Triphenylsiloxy-5,5-dimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane: Removal of water azeotropically from a mixture of 2,2'-oxybis(5,5-dimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane) (1.58 g; 6.5 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (3.61 g; 13.1 mmol) gave a clear solution which was further concentrated and kept at room temperature. The product slowly crystallised out as a white solid (3.65 g, m.p. 126°) (Found: B, 2.69; Si, 7.10%; M, 375. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₅BO₂Si; B, 2.79; Si, 7.24%; M, 388).

2-Triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxaborolane: Azeotropic removal of water with benzene (60 ml) from a mixture of ethane-1,2-diol (0.59 g; 9.5 mmol), boric acid (0.59 g; 9.5 mmol) and triphenylsilanol (2.63 g; 9.5 mmol) gave a colourless viscous liquid (3.29 g, 100%) (Found: B, 3.01; Si, 7.81%; M, 328. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₉BO₂Si; B, 3.13; Si, 8.12%; M, 346). The product (2.01 g) on distillation under reduced pressure yielded a white solid (0.80 g, b.p. 195°/1.5 mm; m.p. 81) (Found: B, 6.57%).

A number of other 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxaborinanes, -borolanes, -borole and -borin were

synthesized by the above procedure. The experimental details are summarised in Table 1.

Amine complexes of 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole: (a) Heat was evolved on adding pyridine (0.20 g; 2.5 mmol) to a solution of 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole (0.61 g; 1.6 mmol) in benzene (15 ml). Excess of solvent and pyridine was removed *in vacuo*, leaving a white solid (0.73 g, m.p. 163°) (Found: B, 2.14; N, 2.45. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄BNO₂Si; B, 2.29; N, 2.96%).

(b) A reddish solid complex (0.54 g, m.p. 144°) was precipitated on adding triethylamine (0.13 g; 1.3 mmol) to a benzene (5 ml) solution of 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole (0.43 g; 1.1 mmol) (Found: B, 2.09; N, 2.79. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₄BNO₂Si; B, 2.19; N, 2.83%).

(c) A white solid complex (1.61 g, m.p. 189°) was similarly obtained from aniline (0.31 g; 3.3 mmol) and 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole (1.30 g; 3.3 mmol) in benzene (20 ml) (Found: B, 2.15; N, 2.59. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₆NBO₂Si; B, 2.22; N, 2.88%).

Reaction between tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane and acetic acid: On adding acetic acid (0.76 g; 12.7 mmol) to a solution of *tris*(triphenylsiloxy)borane (3.48 g; 4.2 mmol) in benzene (20 ml) and refluxing the mixture for 3 hr, boric acid (0.21 g, 78%) was precipitated out (Found: B, 16.9. Calcd. for H₃BO₃; B, 17.5%). The filtrate on removal of solvent gave triphenylacetoxysilane (3.97 g, m.p. 96°) (Found: OCOCH₃, 18.16; Si, 8.42. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅O₂Si; OCOCH₃, 18.55; Si, 8.83%).

Reaction between B(OPr)₃ and Ph₂Si(OH)₂ in 2:3 molar ratio: Tri(isopropoxy)borane (0.68 g; 3.6 mmol), diphenylsilane diol (1.15 g; 5.3 mmol) and benzene on being refluxed for 2 hr and then fractionated, yielded isopropanol (Found: 0.20 g. Calcd. 0.22 g) in the azeotrope and the product (1.15 g, m.p. 212-23°) as a white solid (Found: B, 3.21; Si, 12.53. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₀B₂O₆Si₂; B, 3.26; Si, 12.68%).

Reaction between boric acid and $Ph_2Si(OH)_2$ in 2 : 3 molar ratio : A mixture of boric acid (0.22 g ; 3.6 mmol) and diphenylsilane diol (1.14 g ; 5.3 mmol) in benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. Water was removed azeotropically, followed by drying *in vacuo*. A white solid, (1.12 g, m.p. 212-23°) was obtained as the resulting compound (Found : B, 3.17 ; Si, 12.38. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{30}B_2O_6Si_3$; B, 3.26 ; Si 12.68%).

Reaction between $PhB(OH)_2$ and $Ph_2Si(OH)_2$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio : On removal of water from a mixture of phenyldihydroxyborane (0.58 g ; 4.8 mmol) and diphenylsilane diol (1.03 g ; 4.8 mmol) in benzene (40 ml), followed by drying the product under reduced pressure, a colourless semisolid (1.33 g) was obtained as the final product (Found : B, 3.55 ; Si, 9.16% ; M, 642. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}BO_2Si$; B, 3.58 ; Si, 9.30% ; M, 302).

Reaction between $PhB(OH)_2$ and $Ph_2Si(OH)_2$ in 1 : 2 molar ratio : Water was removed azeotropically from a mixture of phenyldihydroxyborane (0.37 g ; 3.0 mmol) and diphenylsilane diol (1.30 g ; 6.0 mmol) in benzene (60 ml). Removal of excess benzene gave the product (1.50 g) as a colourless semisolid ; (Found : B, 2.06 ; Si, 11.10% ; M, 530. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{25}BO_3Si_2$; B, 2.16 ; Si, 11.23% ; M, 500).

Reactions between boric acid, $Ph_2Si(OH)_2$ and a diol in 2 : 1 : 2 molar ratio : (a) Azeotropic dehydration with benzene (60 ml) of a mixture of boric acid (1.15 g, 18.5 mmol), pinacol (2.20 g ; 18.6 mmol) and diphenylsilane diol (2.00 g ; 9.3 mmol) yielded a colourless viscous liquid (4.33 g) (Found : B, 4.56 ; Si, 5.92% ; M, 452. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{24}B_2O_6Si$; B, 4.63 ; Si, 6.00% ; M, 468).

(b) Reaction between boric acid (2.00 g ; 32.3 mmol), butane-1,3-diol (2.90 g ; 32.2 mmol) and diphenylsilane diol (3.48 g ; 16.1 mmol) was carried out as in the previous experiment, yielding a colourless viscous liquid (6.57 g) (Found : B, 5.19 ; Si, 6.75% ; M, 401. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{26}B_2O_6Si$; B, 5.25 ; Si, 6.82% ; M, 412).

Results and Discussion

Phenyl bis(triphenylsiloxy)borane and tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane have been obtained in quantitative yields by the following routes :

Both these compounds are white crystalline solids, soluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and other common organic solvents. The ease of preparation of tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane from tri(isopropoxy)borane may be compared with attempted synthesis of tri(*tert*-butoxy)borane from lower trialkoxyboranes. The reaction of tri(methoxy)borane and

tri(ethoxy)borane with excess *tert*-butanol stops after the removal of 2 moles of methanol and ethanol respectively⁸. The facile nature of silanolysis in comparison to alcoholysis is perhaps due to higher acidity of silanols.

Attempts to synthesize mixed (isopropoxy)-(triphenylsiloxy)boranes, $(Pr^iO)_2(Ph_2SiOB)$ and $(Pr^iO)(Ph_2SiO)_2B$, either by the interaction of tri(isopropoxy)borane with triphenylsilanol in the appropriate molar ratio or by codisproportionation reaction between $B(OPr^i)_3$ and $B(OSiPh_3)_3$ in refluxing benzene were unsuccessful. Only tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane was obtained as the final product in all these reactions after removing the volatiles under reduced pressure.

The pmr spectra of mixtures of $B(OPr^i)_3$ and $B(OSiPh_3)_3$ in 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 molar ratios in CCl_4 show three sets of isopropoxy methyl doublets in the region 8.6-9.1 τ . The absorption due to aromatic protons occurs as a broad-based peak at 2.2-2.9 τ which is split into three sharp peaks at the apex. This indicates that all the following four species are present in equilibrium :

These observations are similar to those for unsymmetrical trialkoxy boranes and are in contrast to the reported isolation⁹ of $(Et_3SiO)_2BOME$, which probably needs rechecking.

In contrast to simple alkoxy siloxyboranes, the unsymmetrical cyclic derivatives show considerable thermal stability and can be readily synthesized by a number of routes. For example, 2-triphenylsiloxy-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborinane, which distils unchanged at 217°/0.05 mm, has been obtained by the following routes :

However, the simplest and most convenient route for the synthesis of 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxaborolanes, -borinanes, -borole and -borin appears to be the azeotropic removal of water from an equimolar mixture of a diol, boric acid and tri-

All the above compounds are obtained quantitatively in pure state without any trace of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SiO-G-O-SiPh}_3$ and are generally white solids except the propane-1,2-diol and catechol derivatives which are colourless viscous liquids. All of these are monomeric in refluxing benzene. Like other alkoxyboranes, these compounds are also sensitive towards moisture and hydrolyse to yield the diol, boric acid and triphenylsilanol. Attempts to carry out partial hydrolysis were unsuccessful and it could not be determined whether B-O-Si linkage is initially cleaved or the B-O-C linkage. Most of these triphenylsiloxy derivatives can be distilled unchanged (at $\sim 200^\circ$) under reduced pressure (~ 0.1 mm). Ethane-1,2- and propane-1,3-diol derivatives, however, distil with some decomposition leaving a solid residue which appears to be a mix-

ture of $\text{B(OSiPh}_3)_3$ and $(\text{OG O-B})_2\text{O}$. The characteristic peaks of triphenylsilyl moiety in the ir spectra of triphenylsiloxyboranes are (i) two weak but sharp bands in the $3025\text{-}3070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region due to aromatic C-H stretching modes, (ii) peaks at 1430 cm^{-1} (masked by nujol absorption in solid samples) and 1120 cm^{-1} (the latter

being one of the strongest peaks in the spectra) due to silicon-phenyl linkage and (iii) a set of four peaks at $740, 710, 700$ and 670 cm^{-1} (the middle peaks being stronger than the outer ones) due to mono-substituted benzene ring. A strong intensity peak due to $\nu_{\text{as}} \text{B-O-Si}$ appears at 1315 cm^{-1} in $\text{B(OSiPh}_3)_3$ which is comparable to its position at $1333 \pm 8\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in *tris*(trialkylsiloxy)boranes¹⁰. The ir spectra of 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxaborolanes and borinanes show $\nu_{\text{as}} \text{B-O-Si}$ at $1300\text{-}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu_{\text{as}} \text{B-O-C}$ at $1350\text{-}1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the latter being much stronger than the former.

The pmr spectrum of $\text{B(OSiPh}_3)_3$ shows a single broad based ($2.3\text{-}2.9\tau$) peak with an apex at 2.75τ for the aromatic protons. This broad peak is much better resolved in the spectra of the cyclic derivatives which show two complex multiplets in the region $2.2\text{-}2.55\tau$ (due to two *ortho* protons) and $2.85\text{-}2.90\tau$ (due to *meta* and *para* protons). The strong deshielding effect of silicon on *ortho* protons is probably due to donation of aromatic π electrons to the d-orbitals of silicon. Other peaks due to the alkanedioxy moieties are present at expected positions and the data are summarised in Table 2.

Tris(triphenylsiloxy)borane and 2-triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-dioxaborolanes and -borinanes do not appear to react with amines. 2-Triphenylsiloxy-1,3,2-benzodioxaborole, on the other hand, reacts exothermally with nitrogen donors (e.g. pyridine, triethylamine and aniline) to form solid adducts of 1:1 composition in which coordination occurs from nitrogen to boron.

TABLE 2—RELEVANT PMR AND IR DATA

Sl. No	G=	Chemical shift (τ) and shape	Assignment	$\nu_{\text{B-O-Si}}$ (cm^{-1})
1.	$-\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_2}-$	6.00, s	a	1315
2.	$-\overset{\text{c}}{\text{CH}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}-$	8.85, d, $J=6$ cps 5.40-6.70, m	a b+c	1325
3.	$-\overset{\text{a}}{\text{C}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})_2\overset{\text{a}}{\text{C}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})_2-$	8.90, s	a	1315
4.	$-\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}-$	8.25, q, $J=5.5$ cps 6.10, t	a b	1335
5.	$-\overset{\text{d}}{\text{CH}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{c}}{\text{CH}_2}-$	8.95, d, $J=6$ cps 8.20-8.75, m 5.80-6.30, m	a b o+d	1325
6.	$-\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{a}}{\text{C}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})_2\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_2}-$	9.22, s 6.54, s	a b	1335
7.	$-\overset{\text{a}}{\text{C}}(\overset{\text{a}}{\text{CH}_3})_2\overset{\text{c}}{\text{CH}_2}\overset{\text{d}}{\text{CH}}(\overset{\text{b}}{\text{CH}_3})-$	8.97, overlapping s and d 8.30-8.30, m 5.50-6.30, m	a+b c d	1310
8.	$o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	2.1-3.3, m	a	1325
9.	$o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2-$	4.9, s 2.0-3.3, m	a b	1300

B-O-Si linkage in triphenylsiloxyboranes appears to be much less reactive than B-O-Ge and B-O-Sn linkages in germanoxy- and stannoxy-boranes^{1,1a}. Thus, under the same conditions where the latter two linkages are cleaved, the B-O-Si linkage remains unaffected as shown by lack of reaction with acetic anhydride, succinic anhydride and phenyl isocyanate. B(OSiPh₃)₃, however, reacts readily with acetic acid in 1:3 molar ratio in refluxing benzene yielding boric acid and triphenylsilyl acetate and presumably involving Si-O bond cleavage.

Diphenylsildioxy derivatives: Condensation of tri(isopropoxy)borane or boric acid with diphenylsilane diol in 2:3 molar ratio in refluxing benzene yields a white crystalline product which is soluble in benzene and melts in a wide range of temperature (212-23°):

Attempts to determine the molecular weight of this compound by ebulliometry were unsuccessful due to the negligible change in the resistance even on taking a sufficiently large amount of the compound. Such behaviour is generally shown by highly polymeric compounds and therefore we believe that the compound is polymeric (Structure I).

Condensation of phenyldihydroxyborane and diphenylsilane diol in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios in refluxing benzene yields cyclic derivatives II and III as viscous semi solids. The pmr spectra of all the three products show only a complex multiplet in the aromatic region (2.0-3.0 τ).

Reaction of diphenylsilane diol with boric acid and a diol (e.g. pinacol or butane-1,3-diol) in 1:2:2 molar ratio in refluxing benzene yields the corresponding diphenyldi(boroxy)silanes (IV and V) as monomeric viscous liquids which are soluble in common organic solvents and decompose during attempted distillation.

The ir and pmr spectra of these compounds show close resemblance to those of the corresponding triphenylsiloxy derivatives. For the sake of comparison, it may be mentioned that the corresponding dialkyldi(boroxy)germanes can also be isolated as stable compounds^{1a}. However, dialkyldi(boroxy)tin derivatives do not appear to be stable and are readily converted into di(boroxy)tetraalkyldistannoxanes¹⁴.

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References

- M. F. LAPPERT and G. J. LEIGH (Ed.), "Developments in Inorganic Polymer Chemistry", Elsevier, 1962.
- W. A. G. GRAHAM and F. G. A. STONE (Ed.), "Inorganic Polymers", Academic Press, New York, 1962.
- H. SCHMIDBAUR, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1965, 4, 201.
- F. SCHINDLER and H. SCHMIDBAUR, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1967, 6, 688.
- H. STEINBERG, "Organoboron Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1964, Vol 1.
- N. F. ORLOV, B. N. DOLGOV and M. G. VORONKOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Otd. Khim. Nauk*, 1960, 1607.
- S. K. MEHROTRA, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1974, 4, 27.
- G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, Unpublished results.
- E. WIBERG and U. KRUEKKE, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1953, 8B, 610.
- E. W. ABEL and A. SINGH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 690.
- S. K. MEHROTRA, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 73, 277.
- S. K. MEHROTRA, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 65, 367.
- S. K. MEHROTRA, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 163.
- S. K. MEHROTRA, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 65, 367.